

MODERN LEARNING METHODS IN THE DISTANT MEDICAL EDUCATION: EFFECTIVENESS AND WAYS OF IMPROVEMENT**Shuper Vira Olexandrivna***Ph.D., MD, Associate Professor of the Department of Internal Medicine, Clinical Pharmacology and Occupational Diseases, Higher State Educational Establishment of Ukraine "Bukovinian State Medical University",***Shuper Serhii Victorovich***Ph.D., MD, Associate Professor of the Department of physical rehabilitation, Occupational therapy and Pre-medical assistance**Yuri Fedkovich Chernivtsi National University***Abstract**

In present work we described and discussed modern learning methods in the distant medical education, their effectiveness and ways of improvement. Higher educational institutions of medical education are faced with the need to master and implement new methods of digital media technologies and the application of digitization at all levels of training of medical specialists. A special place in collaborative medical education is occupied by Problem-Based and Project-Oriented Learning methods, which are based on an activity approach in assimilation and processing of information. Problem-Based and Project-Oriented Learning methods with Web Quests can be provided easily and widely into modern medical education process to improve the effectiveness of distance learning.

Keywords: distance learning, medical education, digital media technologies, Problem-Based and Project-Oriented Learning methods.

Introduction. The COVID-19 pandemic, wars and cataclysms all over the world have affected the way of teaching and learning in general and medicine education also. Higher educational institutions of medical education are faced with the need to master and implement new methods of digital media technologies and the application of digitization at all levels of training of medical specialists. Digitization of teaching and learning formats in education and training in the field of medicine requires the creation of didactic materials with digital support, the use of appropriate digital and communication tools, the implementation of the latest effective teaching methods, as well as the digital literacy of all participants in the learning process [1, 2].

Basically, distance learning, also known as digital learning comprises digital teaching materials, digital delivery, digital tools, and independent learning. It allows students to choose the way they study in a mixture of both synchronous and asynchronous variants without the restriction of time and location [1]. The development of an online platform especially the Learning Management System (LMS) offers a 'blended learning' environment for the students where they can communicate with lecturers, submit their assignments, discuss with peers, and share group work through the platform [3].

A student's educational motivation forms behavior aimed at academic achievement and is a key success factor, especially in the distant version of knowledge acquisition. Many factors influence learning motivation, including age and gender, interpersonal relation such as academic factors, cognitive and emotional characteristics of the learners and the learning supervisor, including anxiety and depression, and behavioral outcomes such as academic inclusion.

Aim of the study was to describe and discuss modern learning methods in the distant medical education, their effectiveness and ways of improvement.

Results and discussion. According to definition, «Distributed and distance learning is a varied and

planned course of study, designed and developed to address the curriculum for students who are in different locations away from the central teaching institution, supported by teaching and supervisory staff who are also physically or virtually distributed across those locations. Distributed and distance learning is a whole-systems approach, including all teaching and learning, formative and summative assessments, feedback on learning, support for students and teachers, management, and quality assurance.

Distributed and distance learning can encompass technology-based and non-technology-based educational methods and experiences. Distributed and distance learning might refer to an entire course, or a part of it» [4].

A special place in collaborative medical education is occupied by Problem-Based and Project-Oriented Learning methods, which are based on an activity approach in assimilation and processing of information. Problem-Based Learning is a learning method in which real complex problems are used as an educational tool. Such training is based on problem solving, stimulates medical students to apply critical thinking skills to solve problems in a limited time, provides real experience that promotes an active learning process, helps to systematize knowledge and naturally integrates the educational process and real professional activity [2, 5].

Interdisciplinary in nature, problematic tasks differ among themselves, but there are some common characteristics:

- the problem should stimulate students to seek a deeper understanding of concepts or theories;
- the problem should require that the participants make informed decisions with further protection;
- the problem should contain such tasks that, in order to solve them, students need to connect them with previous courses or knowledge;
- the problem that is solved in groups should correspond to such a level of complexity to stimulate students to achieve a common goal [5].

Project-Oriented methods in distance education allow students to be involved in the active cognitive process, learn to work in cooperation, performing various social roles, obtain the necessary information and process it, argue and present the results of their activities.

Common features of Problem-Based and Project-Oriented Learning are:

- involvement of real problems and situations (for example, clinical cases and situations) in the educational process;
- are based on real educational goals;
- include intermediate (staged) and final evaluation of the work;
- education seekers - in the center of educational activity, the teacher - the head of educational research;
- motivation of educational activity;
- interdisciplinary;
- give an opportunity to practice the skills of cooperation, problem solving, applying critical thinking in the work process.

At the same time, there is a significant difference between Problem-Based Learning and Project-Oriented Learning: Problem-Based Learning focuses on a problem and the process of solving it, and for Project-Oriented Learning, the main goal is to get a final product [6].

Project-Oriented Learning in distance education is implemented through the Web-Quest method, which is created in order for students to learn how to use the received information for a practical purpose. Real placement of Web Quests on the network in the form of websites created by students themselves allows to significantly increase their motivation and achieve better educational results.

The development of project learning technologies, computer and Web technologies led to emergence and widespread use of Web-Quest technology in the educational process - pages on Internet sites that contain hyperlinks to other pages on a certain topic [7].

The Web-Quest method is a problematic task transformed into an interesting journey through the Internet with elements of a role-playing game, which involves queries in various search engines to obtain a significant amount of information, its analysis, systematization and subsequent presentation in the form of creative projects.

This method of interactive learning involves group work of three to five people and allows to increase motivation for learning, expand the professional intellect, develop search and research skills, the ability to use Internet resources important for learning, and develop creative thinking.

Web quests for solving controversial problems involve finding and presenting different, and sometimes conflicting, opinions on the same problem and trying to bring them to a consensus.

Analytical Web quest explores the relationship of real-world things within a given topic. Such tasks provide a basis for medical students to acquire knowledge in the conditions under which they have to carefully study things, find common and different, as well as find hidden similar phenomena, understand the connection of causes and effects, discussing their meaning.

Scientific Web quests serve to introduce and engage medical students in scientific research in various fields of knowledge [8].

Discussed effective learning methods do not cause difficulties in their application in the educational process, because they do not require downloading additional programs or possessing additional technical knowledge and skills. So, Problem-Based and Project-Oriented Learning methods with Web Quests can be provided easily and widely into modern medical education process [8, 9].

Conclusions.

Thus, distance education gives medical students access to non-traditional sources of information, increases the efficiency of independent work, provides completely new opportunities for creativity, finding and consolidating various professional skills, and allows teachers to implement fundamentally new forms and methods of learning which is naturally added to traditional medical education.

Distance learning involves an approach to the development of the whole course more than simply converting existing offline learning to other means or methods that are accessible to non-face-to-face students. Students and teachers involved in distance learning need special training, information, guidance and support.

Curricula for distance learning must be specially designed taking into account needs and circumstances of the learning environment of the students and teachers, it must ensure the same quality of education, teaching and assessment as on-site learning, including interpersonal interaction between students and communication between students and teachers. Providing regular personal feedback on student studying performance in distance learning should be constant and high-quality for both students and teachers.

References

1. Lee, J. X., Ahmad Azman, A. H., Ng, J. Y., & Ismail, N. A. S. (2023). Open Distance Learning in Medical Education: Does It Improve Students' Motivation? *Sage Open*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231157687>
2. Liakhovskiy V.I., Nemchenko I.I., Lysenko R.B. (et all.) (2023). Peculiarities of distance education in institutions of higher medical education. *Actual Problems of the Modern Medicine: Bulletin of Ukrainian Medical Stomatological Academy*, 23, 129-132. <https://doi.org/10.31718/2077-1096.23.1.129>.
3. Adams D., Sumintono B., Mohamed A., Noor N. S. M. (2018). E-learning readiness among students of diverse backgrounds in a leading Malaysian higher education institution. *Malaysian Journal of Learning and Instruction*, 15(2), 227–256. <https://doi.org/10.32890/mjli2018.15.2.9>
4. World federation of medical education. STANDARDS FOR DISTRIBUTED AND DISTANCE LEARNING IN MEDICAL EDUCATION. 2021. 48 p.
5. Chorna I.O., Yaroshenko R.A., Zubakha A.B., Shumeiko I.A., Drabovskiy V.S. (2024). Distance learning methods for international medical students. *Actual Problems of the Modern Medicine: Bulletin of*

Ukrainian Medical Stomatological Academy, 24, 204-208. <https://doi.org/10.31718/2077-1096.24.1.204>.

6. Utterback E. M. The Effect of Problem-Based Learning on Motivation, Engagement, and Teacher Efficacy. 2023. 214 p.

7. Fadhilah M., Sutrisna S., Muslimah S. N., Ihsan, M. T. (2021). An exploring methods in online learning: Synchronous and asynchronous. *ETDC: Indonesian Journal of Research and Educational Review*, 1(1), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.51574/ijrer.v1i1.55>

8. Suh I., McKinney T., Siu K-C. (2023). Current Perspective of Metaverse Application in Medical Education, Research and Patient Care. *Virtual Worlds*, 2(2), 115-128. <https://doi.org/10.3390/virtual-worlds2020007>.

9. Siripipattanakul S., Sriboonruang P., Kaewpuang P., Limna, P. Jaipong P., Sitthipon T. (2023). Problem-Based Learning in the Digital Era. *Multidisciplinary Approaches to Research*. 2023. № 1. P. 209-217.